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Solid flux measurement in dual fluidized bed processes based on solid samples[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Chemical looping gasification is a novel dual fluidized bed technology for the conversion of solid feedstock to a nitrogen-free syngas without the need of pure oxygen. Recently, a pilot plant has been erected to advance chemical looping gasification towards autothermal operation. For autothermal operation, the solids flux between the two reactors becomes important, as it transports the required sensible heat in addition to the oxygen required for the process. As a reliable method to accurately measure the solids flux under process conditions currently does not exist, a method has been devised to measure the solid circulation for dual fluidized bed systems and tested utilizing the process specifics of chemical looping gasification to allow for calibration of online measurement equipment without opening the reactor system. This method utilizes solid samples from coupling elements to calculate the solids flux in chemical looping gasification with an overall uncertainty smaller than 20%.

1. Introduction

Spurred by the increasing pace of climate change, research in carbon neutral and carbon negative processes has increased in order to combat the global warming. One focus is the decarbonization of the transport sector. While for road transport electrification is a viable option, aviation and maritime transport require different approaches. Here, the production of bio-fuels using the well-known Fischer–Tropsch process is one option. However, thermal conversion of biomass into the required syngas for the synthesis step is still not commercialized although efforts have been made for dual fluidized bed gasification [1,2]. One process offering the possibility of virtually no CO₂ emissions, when combined with a suitable separation step during gas cleaning, is CLG, which has seen increasing research activity into scale up. It utilizes a metal oxide powder, which is cyclically oxidized and reduced while being transported back and forth between two fluidized bed reactors, to supply oxygen to the gasification process without the need for an expensive air separation unit.

CLG has been successfully demonstrated in lab scale using coal with synthetic OC materials [3], biomass with synthetic OC [4–6] and with biomass and natural minerals like haematite [7,8] or ilmenite [9]. Even waste materials have been tried as OC materials [10]. Advances

towards autothermal operation are being made using simulations [11, 12] and by design of a pilot plant [13]. These advances stress the importance of the OC not only for the transport of oxygen, but also for the transport of sensible heat from FR to AR as high heating demands inside the FR cannot be compensated by external electrical reactor heating for successful process deployment. However, reliable measurements of the solids circulation are difficult to obtain. Moreover, the solids transported from the FR towards the AR consist not only of the reduced OC material, but include also a fraction of unconverted feedstock in the form of fixed carbon, called carbon slip, and ash. Methods to obtain quantitative data for the OC circulation between the reactors can be classified as online, offline, invasive and non-invasive [14]. Additionally simulation and cold-flow studies can be used to generate the data afterwards. Nonetheless, for elaborate and expensive experiments as described in [13] the measurement of solid circulation during the experiments and from material samples results in far more reliable data than a posteriori generated data from cold flow models or simulation.

Stollhof et al. [15] investigated methods to estimate the solid circulation rate based on the amount of fluidization medium, particle properties and pressure profile in the reactors which can be applied

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Abbreviations

AR	Air reactor
CFB	Circulating fluidized bed
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CLC	Chemical looping combustion
CLG	Chemical looping gasification
FI	Flow indicator
FR	Fuel reactor
GA	Gas analysis
LS	Loop seal
OC	Oxygen carrier
PA	Proximate analysis
PSD	Particle size distribution
SP	Sample point
UA	Ultimate analysis

Symbols

LHV	Lower heating value (MJkg^{-1} , MJmol^{-1})
R_{OC}	Oxygen transport capacity
T	Temperature (K, °C)
W	Molar mass, atomic mass (kgmol^{-1})

X_S	Oxidation degree
\dot{m}	Mass flow (kgs^{-1})
m	Mass (kg)
x	Mass fraction in solid phase
y	Mass fraction in gas phase
N_2	Nitrogen

Subscripts

C	Carbon
Gas	Gas phase
LS	Loop seal
OC	Oxygen carrier
O	Oxygen
S	Solid
e	End of oxidation in stream entering reactor
i	Chemical species
j	Chemical species
out	Stream leaving reactor
ox	Oxidized real start mass including carbon
red	Reduced
$scale$	Weighing scale
s	Start of oxidation
$total$	Sum of all components

Superscripts

f	Hypothetical state at oxidation start
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to the hot reactor system. However, a reported deviation of $\pm 40\%$ is discouraging as such deviations in solid circulation could potentially result in a FR temperature drop of more than 150 K [11] negatively impacting conversion and syngas quality. Smaller deviations have been reported using empirical adjustments. However, fitting to a geometrical similar model is required, and temperature influences seem to be difficult to quantify [16]. Direct measurement using impact force of the particle flow is limited by the maximum permissible temperature

of the measurement equipment and can therefore not be used under process conditions. However, a recent review by Liu et al. [17] suggests a design which might be possible. Online Measurements using optical sensing have been successfully tested in cold flow configurations [18] and in 2D setups [19]. However, the application to large-scale units operating at high temperatures is not possible as the sensor cannot measure deep inside the 3D flow structure of the solid flux or through the refractory lined reactor walls. Other setups using moving mechanical equipment inside the solid flux [20] seem problematic with regards to the lifetime under the harsh process conditions.

Direct online measurement using the microwave and Doppler effect is an option, but usually requires extensive calibration under process conditions [21], which are not feasible, as the loop has to be broken for calibration. It can be calibrated under cold conditions, but the influence of the temperature cannot be reliably predicted and subsequently compensated, as no data is available yet.

Using tracer particles as described in [14] is likely to be of limited use, as attrition and the continuous removal of agglomerates pose the possibility of the removal of the tracer particle. Magnetic tracers are good for cold flow models [22] but refractory lining and Curie temperature pose problems for hot systems. The injection of cold particles and tracking the corresponding temperature drop with thermocouples [23] seems the most viable tracer method. However, as with most tracer methods it requires a uniformly moving packed bed. It becomes generally more difficult to locate small amounts of tracer particles with growing plant size, as tracers can be easily obscured making the methods less accurate.

The solid circulation can be determined via scaling laws based on measurement in a cold flow model with accumulation measurements inside the coupling elements (e.g. loop seals) or with another method. A perfectly scaled cold flow model is difficult to realize for metal powders, as the cold flow model would need to be filled with Helium or use radioactive materials. Not perfectly scaled cold flow models can give a quantitative measurement in the right order of magnitude, but the exact error created cannot be assessed.

Calculations using CFD require validation of the model to allow for an assessment of the quality of the generated data. However, during endeavours of upscaling such models extrapolate far outside their validation range, as the data to be obtained is the data required for validation. Theoretically, the solid circulation is obtainable via the heat balance. However, accurate knowledge of heat losses can be obtained for indoor laboratory units [24,25] but estimation of heat losses for large scale industry plants through the refractory lined reactor walls under changing ambient outdoor conditions is challenging. Methods using balances around a heat exchanger removing sensible heat from the bed material [26] are applicable to CFB boilers but not in CLG where the bed material is used to heat the FR.

Linderholm et al. describe a method which uses batch wise fuel feeding and measuring of system response time to determine the solid circulation in an externally heated reactor system fed with coal [27]. However, application seems impossible when using fuels high in volatiles like biomasses where changes in fuel feed severely impact reactor hydrodynamic. Furthermore, under autothermal condition the fuel feed is directly impacting system temperature, reactor chemistry, and gas velocity and would therefore significantly alter the solid discharge in CFB reactors. The introduction of a mechanical device to divert and sample the entire solids flow are successfully deployed in small scale units [9]. However, at larger units these become very difficult to operate and the sampled volume impractical to handle. The general applicability of different measurement technologies to industry sized plants is discussed by Liu et al. [17].

This study proposes a new method utilizing solid samples taken from coupling elements and the specifics of the process to obtain the solid circulation from experimental operation with no dependence on reactor geometry. Moreover, the error can be quantified by the calculation of the propagated uncertainties. The underlying calculation and required measurements are presented here in detail.

Fig. 1. Schematic of a dual fluidized bed process indicating relevant streams.

2. Method

Coupled fluidized bed reactors are usually used to periodically load or unload a carrier material with a substance (CLG, CLC [28,29], carbonate looping [30–32] etc.) and even where only heat transport is desired (e.g. dual fluidized bed gasification [33]) some amount of reactive material is transported. To determine the solid circulation, a suitable balance around one reactor can be employed to get accurate information on the solids transport between the reactors. The necessary measurement sites for the gaseous streams (e.g. composition, volume flows) are usually part of any reactor setup as they are used for process control. However, such a balance equation requires information on solids flux composition which is usually not available via online measurements and needs to be taken from offline sample analysis.

A general reactor setup is depicted in Fig. 1 with a boundary for the balance around Reactor 1. Usually one reactor has a simpler chemistry (less components) and requires less assumptions (less reactions or equilibrium reactions) or sample analysis and is therefore simpler to balance. The balance itself can be a mass balance or one or multiple elemental (or molecular) balances and depends on the process. As all processes have a difference in composition in the solids flux entering and leaving a reactor, this difference can be used according to the balance equation to calculate the solids flux transported between the reactors.

Assuming substance i is transported in excess with the solids flux \dot{m}_S and released inside Reactor 1 as a gaseous species, the balance equation is:

$$0 = x_{i,in} \cdot \dot{m}_{S,in} - x_{i,out} \cdot \dot{m}_{S,out} + y_{i,in} \dot{m}_{gas,in} - y_{i,out} \dot{m}_{gas,out} \quad (1)$$

With y_i being the mass fraction of species i in the gas stream, while x_i is the mass fraction in the solids flux expressed as excess quantity. The expression of i as excess quantity, i.e. $\dot{m}_{total} = \dot{m}_S + \dot{m}_i = \dot{m}_S(1 + x_i)$ has the advantages, in case of only one incorporated or released species were \dot{m}_S become equal for inlet and outlet stream. If there is more than one species incorporated or released, the difference of the two solids mass fluxes $\dot{m}_{S,in}$ and $\dot{m}_{S,out}$ must be the difference of all other species j released from or incorporated into the solids flux giving:

$$\Delta \dot{m}_S = -\dot{m}_{S,in} + \dot{m}_{S,out} = \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,in} \cdot \dot{m}_{Gas,in} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,out} \cdot \dot{m}_{Gas,out} \quad (2)$$

And therefore the solids flux entering Reactor 1 can be calculated to be¹:

$$\dot{m}_S = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in}(y_{i,in} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,in} \cdot x_{i,out}) - \dot{m}_{Gas,out}(y_{i,out} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,out} \cdot x_{i,out})}{x_{i,out} - x_{i,in}} \quad (3)$$

The selection of species i should be done according to:

- sample analysis: a species for which the mass fraction inside the sample can easily be analysed
- process: a species which is only present in a few components in the gas phase, reducing the online analysis effort
- reactions: a species which is fast consumed or released inside the reactor reducing the possible impact during transient states

It should be noted that $\Delta \dot{m}_S$ can be zero for processes where only one species is released or incorporated into the solids flux, with the balance equation simplifying accordingly. Moreover, the reference state for x_i can be selected to be either $x_{i,in}$ or $x_{i,out}$ simplifying the equation and probably the laboratory analysis. For the CLG process either oxygen or carbon can be used to balance the AR. The advantage of using carbon is its good availability to sample analysis, while for oxygen the reference state can be selected as $x_{i,in} = 0$ simplifying the equation.

3. Experimental

3.1. 1 MW_{th} pilot plant

A simplified flow sheet of the 1 MW_{th} experimental facility for autothermal operation of the CLG process is shown in Fig. 2 and described in detail elsewhere [13]. It shows the reactor system including the relevant measurement sites and sampling points in the installed loop seals for this method. The OC is oxidized inside the AR which is operated in a CFB mode. The entrained solids are separated via a cyclone and transported towards the AR loop seal. From the AR loop seal the oxidized OC is then transported via a J-valve into the bed of the FR. Inside the FR (also a CFB) the OC is reduced with the feedstock which is fed into the dense zone of the bed. Entrained solids are separated via cyclone and transported through the FR loop seal back to the AR. The amount of solids transported from the AR loop seal towards the FR i.e. the global solid circulation between the reactors, is controlled via the J-valve fluidization. Any material entrained from the AR which exceeds the solids flux through the J-valve is returned to the AR. The measurement sites relevant for the described method are the measurements of the gas flows (FI), the gas composition (GA), and the SPs which are indicated in the flow sheet. The solids fluxes are sampled inside the loop seal sample points (details provided in Section 3.3). Additional streams entering the reactor system are the feedstock going into the FR and propane for heating and co-firing in the AR. The propane can either be fed directly into the bed or via the start-up burner together with air. The OC material make-up flow, which is fed into the AR loop seal, is neglected during calculation as it is two orders of magnitude smaller than the circulating material.

As AR operation in sub-stoichiometric conditions is required to limit the oxygen availability and thus the syngas conversion inside the FR [11–13], it can be assumed that all oxygen in the air flow fed to the AR is consumed making oxygen a good candidate as the species to be balanced. Moreover, the oxidation degree X_S as defined by [34]:

$$X_S = \frac{m_{OC,LS} - m_{OC,red}}{R_{OC} \cdot m_{oc,ox}} = 1 - \frac{m_{OC,ox} - m_{OC,LS}}{R_{OC} \cdot m_{oc,ox}} \quad (4)$$

$$R_{OC} = \frac{m_{OC,ox} - m_{OC,red}}{m_{OC,ox}} \quad (5)$$

¹ Details in Appendix A.1.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the chemical looping gasification process indicating relevant measurement sites, sample position, and balance boundary. FI: flow indicator GA: gas analysis, SP: sample point.

Table 1
Proximate and ultimate analysis of feedstock used during experiments.
LHV: lower heating value, PA: proximate analysis, UA: ultimate analysis.

	Component	Pine forest residue
PA [wt. - %]	Moisture	4.4
	Ash (d.b.)	2.3
	Volatiles (d.b.)	80.3
	Fixed carbon (d.b.)	17.4
UA [wt. - %]	C (d.b.)	51.1
	H (d.b.)	6.1
	N (d.b.)	0.44
	O (d.b.)	40.1
	S (d.b.)	0.025
	Cl (d.b.)	0.010
LHV [MJ kg ⁻¹]		19.70

is an interesting parameter, and its determination gives insight into the performance of the OC material and the overall process. Nonetheless, the balance can be done without exact knowledge of X_S by selecting the reference state for the oxygen fraction transported in excess to the FR output fraction. The laboratory analysis of the oxidation of the OC can then be done with a laboratory oven and a weighing scale. For all calculations in this work an $R_{OC} = 0.033$ is used as determined for used ilmenite by [35]. As the undesired carbon slip from FR towards AR results in a systematic error it has to be corrected by the amount of carbon transported, which requires the additional analysis of the carbon content in the samples. However, the occurrence of carbon slip, although unwanted in practical application of CLG, allows the balance to be done using carbon – as the carbon content requires analysis anyway – without the analysis of the oxygen content or oxidation degree of the OC.

The solid–solid reaction of OC and char inside the loop seals is not considered here. Although solid–solid reactions can occur at the conditions inside the loop seals [36], the OC leaving the FR is already highly reduced, and the low amount of fixed carbon in the feedstock (see Table 1) leads to mass fractions of less than 0.5% carbon inside the

loop seal. Moreover, the mean residence time inside the loop seal is less than a minute making the effect negligible.

Thus the solid flux can be calculated using the AR and either carbon or oxygen as the main species to balance with the other as an additional species incorporated into the OC flux. With carbon as the main species:

$$\dot{m}_{OC} = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in}(y_{C,in} - y_{O,in} \cdot x_{C,out}) - \dot{m}_{Gas,out}(y_{C,out} - y_{O,out} \cdot x_{C,out})}{x_{C,out} - x_{C,in}} \quad (6)$$

or more specific to the gas analysis equipment working on molecular species:

$$\dot{m}_{OC} = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in} \left[\frac{W_C}{W_{CO_2}} y_{CO_2,in} - (y_{O_2,in} + \frac{W_{O_2}}{W_{CO_2}} y_{CO_2,in}) \cdot x_{C,out} \right] - \dot{m}_{Gas,out} \left[\frac{W_C}{W_{CO_2}} y_{CO_2,out} - (y_{O_2,out} + \frac{W_{O_2}}{W_{CO_2}} y_{CO_2,out}) \cdot x_{C,out} \right]}{x_{C,out} - x_{C,in}} \quad (7)$$

with oxygen as main species specific to the gas analysis equipment:

$$\dot{m}_{OC} = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in}(y_{O_2,in} + \frac{W_{O_2}}{W_{CO_2}} y_{CO_2,in}) - \dot{m}_{Gas,out}(y_{O_2,out} + \frac{W_{O_2}}{W_{CO_2}} y_{CO_2,out})}{x_{O,out} - x_{O,in}} \quad (8)$$

Where W is the molar mass of the species, and \dot{m}_{OC} is the OC flux in the reduced state of the process. The additional term results from the fact that oxygen is transported as part of carbon dioxide and reactions between the transported carbon and the provided oxygen. As oxygen is incorporated into the OC flux \dot{m}_{OC} , it has to be accounted for in the case of the carbon balance, whereas carbon is not part of the OC so Eq. (3) simplifies.

For the carbon based balance a suitable reference state for x_C is the carbon free oxygen carrier, while for the oxygen based balance the input concentration $x_{O,in}$ is a better reference state. The consequence

Fig. 3. Particle size distribution of the ilmenite used as oxygen carrier material during experiments.

Fig. 4. Simplified schematic of the sampling setup.

Table 2

Values used for the estimation of the uncertainty (partially from [13]).

	Uncertainty	Unit
$\dot{m}_{Gas,in}$	30	kg h^{-1}
$\dot{m}_{Gas,out}$	30	kg h^{-1}
$y_{O_2,in}$	0,009	
$y_{CO_2,in}$	0,009	
$y_{O_2,out}$	0,009	
$y_{CO_2,out}$	0,009	
$x_{C,in}$	0,0005	
$x_{C,out}$	0,0001	
m_{scale}	1×10^{-10}	kg

The experiments were carried out with pine forest residue as feedstock (analysis in Table 1). Ilmenite with two different PSDs was used as OC material with the PSDs given in Fig. 3. The initial filling of the reactor system (approx. 1000kg) was done with the coarse material and the make up was also the coarse material. During a period of two days fine ilmenite was used as makeup to increase the solid entrainment from the reactors and thus the solid flux between the reactors to decrease the temperature difference ΔT between the reactors and improve process performance.² During the operation of the pilot plant, various operational states of CLC, CLG with propane co-firing in the AR, and autothermal CLG were investigated. Fluidization of the reactor coupling elements was with either N_2 or CO_2 , and the distribution of the streams on the AR and FR output streams was analysed. The carbon and oxygen content of all streams is added to the gas input stream for the calculation accordingly.

All stream data used for the calculation of the solid circulation is averaged for a period of 20 min before the sample time to gain the mean mass flows and gas compositions.

3.3. Sampling procedure

The samples were taken from the standpipe of the two loop seals, where a sampling setup according to Fig. 4 was used. In order to ensure

of choosing $x_{O,in} = 0$ is a reference state which is dependent on the sample point and varies with the sample taken whereas it is constant for the carbon case.

As oxidation of char is favoured over OC oxidation [36–38], $x_{C,out}$ should be zero and the equation simplifies accordingly. However, during experiments the transport of a small amount of unconverted carbon from FR towards AR is observed, so the AR-outlet sample has to be analysed for carbon content.

Based on Eqs. (7) and (8) and the measurement uncertainties (Table 2), the propagated uncertainties of \dot{m}_{OC} is calculated as described in Appendix A.2.2.

3.2. 1 MW_{th} pilot plant operation

The experimental data result from an experimental test campaign using the 1 MW_{th} CLG pilot plant at Technical University of Darmstadt.

² Previous experiments showed high material losses of the fine ilmenite [28, 29]. Additionally the coarse material required no drying prior to usage, resulting in significantly lowered cost. During experiments it was discovered that the required solid circulation could not be reached with the coarse material. Therefore the bed material was gradually replaced with the fine material.

Fig. 5. Set of Samples from air reactor (left) and fuel reactor (right).

samples representing the current process state, the sampling tube was flushed with nitrogen to remove all material in the sampling tube and replace it with new material. The process was observed via infra-red thermometer and was deemed successful when temperatures of 300 °C on the outside were reached. The sample was then discharged from the loop seal via ball valves into a sealed vessel where it was left for cool down for two hours in order to prevent reaction with air oxygen. Afterwards the sample was removed from the system.

It should be noted, that the sample is taken from the outside of the U-shape of the loop seals while most of the solid transport happens on the inside of the U-shape. In fact, depending on loop seal operation a significant zone of stagnant particles has been observed in other units [39]. Therefore, a significant amount of time has to be operated in a steady state for the samples to be truly representative of the operational state. However, the exact time needed is unknown. Nonetheless, under the assumption that the flushing of the sampling setup is successful in removing any stagnant particle zones, the time required in steady-state operation for a representative sample should be in the range required for the whole inventory to cycle once through the system. For the 1 MW_{th} CLG pilot plant with an OC inventory of 1000 kg the time is 4 min to 10 min. Moreover, it is unknown if accumulation of carbon occurs inside the LS or whether the material density influences the distribution inside the LS and thus the representative nature of the samples with regard to the carbon content. Either accumulation or maldistribution might cause a systematic sampling error for the carbon fraction. For the oxygen only the stagnant zones might cause errors, as the oxygen is transported inside the OC lattice structure. However, the nitrogen-flushing during the sampling procedure mitigates errors by stagnant zones.

A typical pair of samples is shown in Fig. 5 where the coarse particles consisting of partially converted feedstock pellets is visible. During the pilot tests the loop seals were sampled over 30 times with a typical sample mass of 0.4 kg to 1.5 kg. Some samples are not considered during the analysis as the sampled mass was below 0.4 kg which is not deemed enough as it indicates a clogged sampling setup and it can therefore not be guaranteed that the sample is representative. All other samples are considered representative for the loop seal and that the actual sample mass has no influence on the accuracy of the method as only small fractions are used for the determination of carbon and oxygen content. Additionally, one sample was discarded as the temperature rise on the sampling setup could not be detected before discharging the material into the sealed sampling container. Therefore the material sampled is at least partially from a previous operating point.

3.4. Sample preparation and analysis

For the analysis of the carbon content the samples were first classified into two particle fractions using a 400 μm sieve. The coarse fraction (containing the majority of the transported carbon) was then crushed to a fine dust in a mortar to be able to process it via a commercially available elemental analysis system (Elementar vario MACRO cube in CHNS setup). The finer fraction was processed in the same system without further preparation. Each fraction was analysed in triplicate with a sample mass of 50 mg using a method providing sufficient oxygen for full oxidation of the carbon and OC material.

From theoretical considerations the carbon content x_c should not exceed 0.5 wt.-% in the FR samples. All samples where x_c exceeds a threshold of 2 wt.-% have therefore been discarded.

For the oxygen balance x_O was determined by oxidizing a sample mass of approx. 5 g in a laboratory oven with the mass being determined before (m_s) and after (m_e) oxidation. The output oxygen fraction is then determined to be³:

$$x_{O,out} = \frac{m_{s,out} m_{e,in}}{m_{e,out} \cdot m_{s,in}} - 1 \quad (9)$$

while the input fraction is always zero. The masses m_s have to be corrected for their carbon content x_c which results in a weight loss during oxidation giving:

$$m_s = \frac{m_{s,real}}{1 - x_c}$$

3.5. Evaluation of measurement method

Based on the described method and the experimental setup the evaluation of the proposed method to calculate the solids flux can only be done during hot operation, as it needs reacting material. However, determining its accuracy is difficult as no good reference method exists. Nonetheless, the plausibility of the values obtained can be checked using results from heat and mass balances used for the design of the experimental facility [13] and by correlation with a quantity known to be directly influenced by the global solid circulation, i.e. the temperature difference between the AR and FR. The higher the solid circulation the smaller the temperature difference between the reactors. The reactor setup (Fig. 2) is done in a way that all material discharged from the

³ Details in Appendix A.1.1.

Fig. 6. Experimental results from chemical looping tests in the 1 MW_{th} range. I: Oxidation degree X_S and carbon content x_c of the collected samples. II: Composition of air reactor gas streams. III: Solid circulation using this papers method, the green region marks the range assumed during the design of the experimental facility [13]. IV: Oxygen and carbon balance from online measurement and from solid circulation and sample composition. V: Temperature difference between air and fuel reactor and oxygen carrier make up stream. Grey background: Periods with major operational adjustments to optimize the process. Patterned background: Period with finer bed material and air reactor operation in oxygen deficient atmosphere.

FR is transported towards the AR and therefore equal to the solid circulation. Hence, the solid circulation should show a correlation to FR gas velocity. Moreover, the calculation is done via the carbon balance and via the oxygen balance giving an indication if the carbon is sampled correctly. If both calculations yield the same result the carbon content is sampled representatively and can be used, otherwise the oxygen based value should be preferred.

4. Results and discussion

The carbon content x_c and the oxidation degree X_S in the valid samples as analysed is depicted in Fig. 6, plot I. It shows two distinct regions for the AR samples in terms of carbon content $x_{c,out}$ and

oxidation degree $X_{S,out}$. At the start there is very low carbon content in these samples caused by the operation of the AR with excess oxygen and $X_{S,out}$ is close to unity. In the later part (indicated by the patterned background) the AR was operated in an oxygen deficient state as described by [11] which leads to an incomplete conversion of the carbon transported from the FR into the AR and to a reduction in X_S . Additionally the fine material was used as OC make up during the later part.

The data for the relevant reactor state is given in Fig. 6, plot II - V and shows the composition of the reactor inlet and outlet gas (II), the solid circulation as calculated by the method presented in Section 2 (III), the oxygen uptake and carbon release inside the AR based on the balance equations of the streams entering and leaving the reactor (IV),

Fig. 7. Solid Circulation over Temperature Difference and fuel reactor gas velocity.

and the temperature difference ΔT between AR and FR with the OC make up stream fed into the reactor (V). The expected range of solid circulation $\dot{m}_{OC}=1.58 \text{ kg s}^{-1}$ to 3.33 kg s^{-1} from the design phase of the experimental facility [13] is indicated in Fig. 6, plot III by the green region.

It can be recognized from the AR gas composition (II) that there are many samples taken during times where major changes in gas composition occur. These are caused by adjustments made to various operation parameters to optimize the CLG process (corresponding times are indicated by the grey background). Here fluctuation of the calculated solid circulation between the two reactors is expected, as the solid circulation is impacted by the adjustments. However, these changes occur over time scales in the range of multiple hours, which is much longer than the required time for the oxygen carrier to cycle through the system, making the method applicable to the data. There exist two longer operation periods where only minor adjustment were performed by the plant operators and where the calculation should yield values with fluctuations not exceeding the uncertainty. However, the high fluctuation of the carbon based calculation Fig. 6, plot III suggests

non representative carbon samples. The oxygen based calculation yields results which fall into the expected range of solid circulation [13] and do not fluctuate as much between consecutive samples. It can be asserted, that during the first phases all except one of the measurements are in the expected region. Nonetheless, the outlier was sampled during a system restart with very low circulation and FR gas velocity (see also Fig. 7) and is therefore likely to be correct. In both plots (II & III) the two distinct modes of operation can also be seen. In plot II, the later part – the oxygen deficient state of the AR – is defined by $y_{O_2,out} = 0$ while in plot III there is a significant increase in oxygen based calculated solid circulation \dot{m}_{OC} .

The carbon and oxygen balance in Fig. 6, plot IV shows the oxygen uptake and carbon release inside the AR. However, when using the carbon based solid circulation and the change ΔX_C from the samples to calculate the oxygen uptake it does match the uptake from the gas flows inside the uncertainty range only for very few samples. This is also indicative of non representative carbon sampling. As such, the other direction – using the oxygen based solid circulation and the change Δx_C from the samples to calculate the carbon release – does neither match the gas phase calculation.

Fig. 8. Relative uncertainty over the difference in the transported species in input and output sample.

In Fig. 6, plot V the temperature difference ΔT between the reactors is given together with the OC make up feed rate \dot{m}_{OC} . The feed of coarse material is indicated in blue, while the fine material is red. Again, the two operational states are clearly visible in the plot as there is a decrease in temperature difference between the reactors as soon as the finer material is fed to the system. The total make up of coarse material fed to the reactor system over the period of 152 h depicted is 932 kg with an average feed rate of $\dot{m}_{OC} = 6.1 \text{ kg h}^{-1}$. In contrast, the total make up of fine material is 1422 kg over 58 h at an average feed rate of $\dot{m}_{OC} = 24.5 \text{ kg h}^{-1}$ replacing the inventory. The removal of bed material is not depicted here.

During the period where the fine OC material was used for make up (indicated by patterned background) the measured solid circulation increases and exceeds the expected range (III). Moreover, when looking at the circulation against the temperature difference between the reactors and the FR gas velocity (Fig. 7) the difference is much smaller with fine OC than with the coarse OC also indicative of the expected and measured higher circulation. The carbon based calculation shows none of the expected trends, further indication that carbon sampling inside the loop seals is not representative. The experimental temperature difference is smaller than the $\Delta T = 100 \text{ K}$ assumed during the design, which is also indicative that the observed solid circulation which is higher than the one assumed during design is true. Moreover, the finer OC material leads to a much higher material discharge from the reactors allowing for a higher solid circulation and thus smaller ΔT which also gives credibility to the measured data. The higher solid circulation also corresponds to higher FR gas velocity as shown in Fig. 7. Therefore, it can be concluded the method gives qualitatively correct and likely also quantitative reliable results when oxygen is used.

Regarding the calculated uncertainty it is clear from Eqs. (7) and (8) that the very small fraction of transported carbon or oxygen during CLG leads to a comparatively high uncertainty, especially when there is very low carbon or high oxygen content in the input sample. Furthermore, as the oxygen transported is in the range 0.6 wt.-% to 1.4 wt.-% whereas the carbon fraction is in the range 0.1 wt.-% to 0.8 wt.-%, uncertainties of the oxygen case based calculation will be lower. The relative uncertainty is depicted in Fig. 8 over the difference of inlet and outlet composition of the transported species ΔX_S and Δx_c . It is immediately visible that the uncertainty of the carbon based calculation is higher than from the oxygen based case. Additionally the oxygen based calculation features lower uncertainty for a higher change in oxidation degree X_S and for lower carbon slip, while the uncertainty

of the carbon based calculation shows only the expected dependency on carbon slip where higher carbon slip results in lower uncertainty.

As oxygen is transported inside the OC lattice structure as part of the particle and not as a separate particle – like carbon – it is the better species to use for the calculation. From the evolution of the uncertainty it can be supposed that the method is likely to give better results if the fraction of the transported and balanced species is higher (e.g. with CO_2 in carbonate looping process). Overall the uncertainty from CLG pilot testing is below 20% using the more reliable species of oxygen which is an improvement when compared to existing methods.

The main issue with the presented data is the question of the representative nature of the samples taken from the loop seals. There is a clear deviation between the carbon based and oxygen based solid flux calculation (Fig. 6, IV), and the carbon based results do not show the expected trends (Fig. 7). Thus, it can be asserted that the sampling of the carbon is not representative, which makes the overall carbon based calculation invalid for the presented data. The oxygen based calculation does not suffer from this problem as it requires correction only for the carbon residing in the sample and is not dependent on the correct sampling of the transported carbon. Here, the remaining issue are regions without material transport inside the loop seal which can potentially influence the sample. However, this is mitigated by the N_2 flushing of the sample line. Both issues can be resolved with taking samples at a location where the samples would be representative, e.g. the down comer pipes below the cyclones.

5. Conclusions

A new method for the calculation of the solid circulation in dual fluidized bed reactor systems has been developed and tested in CLG experiments in the 1 MW_{th} range. It utilizes online measurement of gas flows and compositions of one reactor in combination with balance equations and compositions of solid samples.

- The method can be applied to hot reactor systems without breaking the loop and relies on measurement equipment already required for system control requiring only additional solid sample analysis. The sample point locations must ensure sample compositions representative for the circulated solids.
- The method does not impact reactor hydrodynamic or chemistry in any way.

- For species transported as part of the circulating material lattice structure the time required for steady-state operation is smaller than for species transported outside the lattice structure as separate particles. The actual time depends on reactor size and bed material inventory and lies in the time range required for the bed material inventory to be cycled through the system once.
- Species which are transported as part of the solid lattice should be preferred over species transported in separate particles as it reduces the likelihood of sampling errors.
- The solid circulation determined by the method fluctuates inside the range of the propagated uncertainty for steady-state operation.
- The uncertainty of the method reduces with increasing fraction of the transported and balanced species. The accuracy of solid flux measurement is – depending on the transported species – better than with other available methods. It is below 20% for the presented experimental data with a species which comprises of about 0.6 wt.-% to 1.4 wt.-% of the solids flux.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Falko Marx: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Paul Dieringer:** Investigation, Software, Writing – review & editing. **Jochen Ströhle:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Bernd Epple:** Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Detailed equations

A.1. General equations

$$0 = x_{i,in} \cdot \dot{m}_{S,in} - x_{i,out} \cdot \dot{m}_{S,out} + y_{i,in} \dot{m}_{gas,in} - y_{i,out} \dot{m}_{gas,out} \quad (A.1)$$

$$0 = \dot{m}_{S,in} - \dot{m}_{S,out} + \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,in} \cdot \dot{m}_{Gas,in} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,out} \cdot \dot{m}_{Gas,out} \quad (A.2)$$

$$\Delta \dot{m}_S = -\dot{m}_{S,in} + \dot{m}_{S,out} = \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,in} \cdot \dot{m}_{Gas,in} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,out} \cdot \dot{m}_{Gas,out} \quad (A.3)$$

$$0 = x_{i,in} \cdot \dot{m}_{S,in} - x_{i,out} \left(\dot{m}_{S,in} + \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,in} \cdot \dot{m}_{Gas,in} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,out} \cdot \dot{m}_{Gas,out} \right) + y_{i,in} \dot{m}_{gas,in} - y_{i,out} \dot{m}_{gas,out} \quad (A.4)$$

$$= \dot{m}_{S,in}(x_{i,in} - x_{i,out}) - x_{i,out} \left(\sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,in} \cdot \dot{m}_{Gas,in} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,out} \cdot \dot{m}_{Gas,out} \right) + y_{i,in} \dot{m}_{gas,in} - y_{i,out} \dot{m}_{gas,out} = \dot{m}_{S,in}(x_{i,in} - x_{i,out}) + \dot{m}_{Gas,in}(y_{i,in} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,in} \cdot x_{i,out}) - \dot{m}_{gas,out}(y_{i,out} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,out} \cdot x_{i,out}) - \dot{m}_{Gas,in}(y_{i,in} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,in} \cdot x_{i,out}) - \dot{m}_{Gas,out}(y_{i,out} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,out} \cdot x_{i,out}) \quad (A.5)$$

$$\dot{m}_S = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,out}(y_{i,out} - \sum_{j \neq i} y_{j,out} \cdot x_{i,out})}{x_{i,out} - x_{i,in}}$$

A.1.1. x_O from scale and oven

$$x_{O,in} = \frac{m_{s,in}}{m_{s,in}} - 1 = 0 \quad (A.6)$$

$$x_{O,max} = \frac{m_{e,in}}{m_{s,in}} - 1 \quad (A.7)$$

$$x_{O,out} = \frac{m_{s,out}^f}{m_{s,out}^f} - 1 \quad (A.8)$$

$$m_{e,in} = (1 + x_{O,max})m_{s,in} \quad (A.9)$$

$$m_{e,out} = (1 + x_{O,max})m_{s,out}^f \quad (A.10)$$

$$m_{s,out}^f = \frac{m_{e,out}}{1 + x_{O,max}} \quad (A.11)$$

$$= \frac{m_{e,out}}{1 + \frac{m_{e,in}}{m_{s,in}} - 1} \quad (A.12)$$

$$= \frac{m_{e,out}}{\frac{m_{e,in}}{m_{s,in}}} \quad (A.13)$$

$$= m_{e,out} \cdot \frac{m_{s,in}}{m_{e,in}} \quad (A.14)$$

It follows:

$$x_{O,out} = \frac{m_{s,out}}{m_{e,out} \cdot \frac{m_{s,in}}{m_{e,in}}} - 1 \quad (A.15)$$

$$= \frac{m_{s,out} m_{e,in}}{m_{e,out} \cdot m_{s,in}} - 1 \quad (A.16)$$

Partial derivatives:

$$\frac{\partial x_{O,out}}{\partial m_{s,out}} = \frac{m_{e,in}}{m_{e,out} \cdot m_{s,in}} \quad (A.17)$$

$$\frac{\partial x_{O,out}}{\partial m_{e,out}} = -\frac{m_{s,out} m_{e,in}}{m_{e,out}^2 \cdot m_{s,in}} \quad (A.18)$$

$$\frac{\partial x_{O,out}}{\partial m_{s,in}} = -\frac{m_{s,out} m_{e,in}}{m_{e,out} \cdot m_{s,in}^2} \quad (A.19)$$

$$\frac{\partial x_{O,out}}{\partial m_{e,in}} = \frac{m_{s,out}}{m_{e,out} \cdot m_{s,in}} \quad (A.20)$$

A.2. Derivatives for the calculation of the propagation of uncertainties

A.2.1. Derivatives for oxygen

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial \dot{m}_{Gas,in}} = \frac{y_{O2,in} + \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}} y_{CO2,in}}{x_{O,out} - x_{O,in}} \quad (A.21)$$

Table B.7

Results for the solid circulation including uncertainty from pilot testing. The rows with grey background are taken during reactor restart and shutdown.

Time	Label	Sample mass		$x_{c,in}$	$x_{c,out}$	$X_{S,out}$	$X_{S,in}$	Carbon			Oxygen			ΔT
		AR	FR					\dot{m}_{OC}	$\Delta \dot{m}_{OC}$	$\frac{\Delta \dot{m}_{OC}}{\dot{m}_{OC}}$	\dot{m}_{OC}	$\Delta \dot{m}_{OC}$	$\frac{\Delta \dot{m}_{OC}}{\dot{m}_{OC}}$	
		kg	kg											
20.06. 22:00	CLA2-S-18	0.83	1.51	0,12	0,00	0,74	1,02	4,99	3,36	0,67	3,01	0,31	0,10	86
21.06. 09:54	CLA2-S-22	0.76	1.24	0,50	0,00	0,79	0,97	1,39	0,27	0,19	0,79	0,43	0,55	190
21.06. 12:11	CLA2-S-24	0.84	1.19	0,21	0,01	0,71	0,99	3,96	1,54	0,39	1,91	0,28	0,15	124
21.06. 14:38	CLA2-S-26	0.85	1.39	0,17	0,01	0,64	0,95	4,01	1,83	0,45	2,93	0,26	0,09	104
21.06. 17:27	CLA2-S-28	1.46	1.41	0,26	0,01	0,63	0,97	2,37	0,55	0,23	3,11	0,24	0,08	103
21.06. 20:16	CLA2-S-31	0.43	1.53	0,15	0,00	0,54	0,95	4,30	1,63	0,38	2,21	0,15	0,07	111
21.06. 22:30	CLA2-S-33	1.28	1.06	0,18	0,03	0,51	0,89	4,85	1,81	0,37	2,29	0,17	0,07	112
22.06. 00:30	CLA2-S-35	0.67	0.67	0,33	0,02	0,57	0,85	2,66	0,47	0,18	2,49	0,25	0,10	118
22.06. 01:58	CLA2-S-38	1.31	1.44	0,27	0,03	0,63	0,89	3,80	0,83	0,22	2,08	0,26	0,13	123
22.06. 04:30	CLA2-S-40	0.78	1.43	0,32	0,02	0,72	0,99	3,16	0,57	0,18	2,08	0,26	0,12	129
22.06. 06:00	CLA2-S-42	0.99	1.29	0,54	0,04	0,74	0,99	2,19	0,25	0,11	1,82	0,27	0,15	139
22.06. 10:52	CLA2-S-45	1.05	1.04	0,72	0,03	0,79	0,91	1,92	0,17	0,09	2,21	0,65	0,29	166
22.06. 13:08	CLA2-S-47	1.21	0.60	0,33	0,02	0,76	0,95	3,06	0,72	0,23	2,12	0,41	0,19	152
22.06. 14:52	CLA2-S-51	1.19	0.91	0,33	0,01	0,80	0,97	2,74	0,62	0,23	2,70	0,50	0,19	145
23.06. 00:15	CLA2-S-53	1.58	1.16	0,49	0,01	0,68	0,96	1,88	0,28	0,15	1,84	0,28	0,15	151
23.06. 02:15	CLA2-S-54	1.19	1.43	0,45	0,02	0,69	0,96	1,95	0,33	0,17	2,10	0,29	0,14	137
23.06. 05:15	CLA2-S-59	1.37	0.78	0,17	0,02	0,75	0,95	5,75	2,48	0,43	3,12	0,43	0,14	131
24.06. 21:25	CLA2-S-80	1.41	0.93	0,50	0,02	0,73	0,96	2,07	0,31	0,15	2,76	0,36	0,13	137
25.06. 21:45	CLA2-S-82	1.20	1.04	0,19	0,01	0,81	1,04	4,62	1,46	0,32	3,03	0,34	0,11	131
26.06. 14:20	CLA2-S-92	1.01	1.21	0,43	0,02	0,73	0,95	2,08	0,32	0,16	3,33	0,38	0,11	99
26.06. 16:24	CLA2-S-96	1.08	0.98	0,21	0,02	0,71	0,94	4,62	1,32	0,28	3,72	0,37	0,10	93
26.06. 19:10	CLA2-S-98	0.90	0.76	0,22	0,03	0,61	0,85	4,68	1,49	0,32	3,00	0,33	0,11	96
26.06. 20:51	CLA2-S-100	1.48	1.25	0,32	0,15	0,57	0,77	5,99	2,14	0,36	3,04	0,39	0,13	103
26.06. 23:50	CLA2-S-102	1.42	1.40	0,79	0,06	0,64	0,84	1,50	0,14	0,10	2,64	0,38	0,14	104
27.06. 02:07	CLA2-S-104	1.37	1.45	0,60	0,06	0,59	0,76	1,89	0,24	0,12	3,38	0,49	0,15	77
27.06. 04:45	CLA2-S-106	1.28	1.31	0,23	0,06	0,57	0,70	6,20	2,27	0,37	4,18	0,68	0,16	67
27.06. 06:14	CLA2-S-110	1.39	1.35	0,45	0,12	0,66	0,76	3,03	0,58	0,19	5,55	1,06	0,19	53
27.06. 08:31	CLA2-S-112	1.29	1.36	0,60	0,11	0,61	0,70	2,15	0,29	0,14	5,66	1,14	0,20	56
27.06. 10:02	CLA2-S-114	1.00	1.31	0,74	0,07	0,61	0,71	1,64	0,17	0,10	5,48	1,00	0,18	54
27.06. 12:08	CLA2-S-117	1.33	1.31	0,34	0,07	0,62	0,71	3,85	0,89	0,23	7,64	1,55	0,20	59
27.06. 14:20	CLA2-S-121	0.97	1.39	0,55	0,09	0,60	0,72	2,21	0,31	0,14	5,44	0,81	0,15	51
27.06. 22:50	CLA2-S-126	1.42	1.34	0,38	0,14	0,57	0,70	3,70	0,93	0,25	6,33	0,86	0,14	39
28.06. 02:30	CLA2-S-130	1.08	1.15	0,38	0,15	0,56	0,69	4,38	1,18	0,27	5,10	0,80	0,16	38
28.06. 05:37	CLA2-S-132	1.40	1.35	0,53	0,22	0,63	0,72	3,16	0,62	0,20	7,39	1,51	0,20	37
28.06. 07:51	CLA2-S-136	1.25	1.16	0,51	0,14	0,61	0,74	2,74	0,47	0,17	6,13	0,83	0,14	50
28.06. 10:14	CLA2-S-142	0.87	1.30	0,51	0,10	0,65	0,82	2,09	0,33	0,16	5,53	0,61	0,11	61
28.06. 18:26	CLA2-S-145	0.88	1.13	0,29	0,02	0,50	0,73	3,53	0,76	0,22	3,89	0,37	0,09	85
28.06. 21:46	CLA2-S-149	0.66	0.57	0,92	0,19	0,79	0,86	1,38	0,13	0,10	3,61	1,14	0,32	109

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial \dot{m}_{Gas,out}} = \frac{-(y_{O2,out} + \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}} y_{CO2,out})}{x_{O,out} - x_{O,in}} \tag{A.22}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial y_{CO2,in}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in} \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}}}{x_{O,out} - x_{O,in}} \tag{A.23}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial y_{CO2,out}} = -\frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,out} \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}}}{x_{O,out} - x_{O,in}} \tag{A.24}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial y_{O2,in}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in}}{x_{O,out} - x_{O,in}} \tag{A.25}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial y_{O2,out}} = -\frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,out}}{x_{O,out} - x_{O,in}} \tag{A.26}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial x_{O,in}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in}(y_{O2,in} + \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}} y_{CO2,in}) - \dot{m}_{Gas,out}(y_{O2,out} + \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}} y_{CO2,out})}{(x_{O,out} - x_{O,in})^2} \tag{A.27}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial x_{O,out}} = -\frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in}(y_{O2,in} + \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}} y_{CO2,in}) - \dot{m}_{Gas,out}(y_{O2,out} + \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}} y_{CO2,out})}{(x_{O,out} - x_{O,in})^2} \tag{A.28}$$

A.2.2. Derivatives for carbon

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial \dot{m}_{Gas,in}} = \frac{y_{C,in} - y_{O,in} \cdot x_{C,out}}{x_{C,out} - x_{C,in}} \tag{A.29}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial \dot{m}_{Gas,out}} = \frac{y_{C,out} - y_{O,out} \cdot x_{C,out}}{x_{C,out} - x_{C,in}} \tag{A.30}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial y_{CO2,in}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in}(\frac{W_C}{W_{CO2}} - \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}} x_{C,out})}{x_{C,out} - x_{C,in}} \tag{A.31}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial y_{CO2,out}} = -\frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,out}(\frac{W_C}{W_{CO2}} - \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}} x_{C,out})}{x_{C,out} - x_{C,in}} \tag{A.32}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial y_{O2,in}} = -\frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in} \cdot x_{C,out}}{x_{C,out} - x_{C,in}} \tag{A.33}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial y_{O2,out}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,out} \cdot x_{C,out}}{x_{C,out} - x_{C,in}} \tag{A.34}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial x_{C,in}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in}(\frac{W_C}{W_{CO2}} y_{CO2,in} - (y_{O2,in} + \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}} y_{CO2,in}) \cdot x_{C,out}) - \dot{m}_{Gas,out}(\frac{W_C}{W_{CO2}} y_{CO2,out} - (y_{O2,out} + \frac{W_{O2}}{W_{CO2}} y_{CO2,out}) \cdot x_{C,out})}{(x_{C,out} - x_{C,in})^2} \tag{A.35}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_{OC}}{\partial x_{C,out}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{Gas,in} \left(\frac{W_C}{W_{CO_2}} y_{CO_2,in} - (y_{O_2,in} + \frac{W_{O_2}}{W_{CO_2}} y_{CO_2,in}) \cdot x_{C,in} \right) + \dot{m}_{Gas,out} \left(\frac{W_C}{W_{CO_2}} y_{CO_2,out} - (y_{O_2,out} + \frac{W_{O_2}}{W_{CO_2}} y_{CO_2,out}) \cdot x_{C,in} \right)}{(x_{C,out} - x_{C,in})^2} \quad (A.36)$$

Appendix B. Results from offline samples

See Table B.7.

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